

An Effective and Efficient Implementation of OBE Framework within Constrained Pakistani Environment to Attain Desired Learning Outcomes

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Received October 15, 2021; Revised December 13, 2021; Accepted January 03, 2022

Abstract

Outcome-Based-Education (OBE) is an academic model emphasizing a curriculum framework that outlines specific measurable outcomes. OBE is committed to providing education that embeds required learning outcomes in the students at the end of any degree program, which is indispensable for pursuing advanced education in related discipline and/or to tackling the practical problems of industry. Following the several inherited advantages of the OBE system, Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC) introduced it in local engineering Higher-Education-Institutions (HEIs), in 2018, replacing previously followed Syllabus and Curriculum-based education system. The previously followed system only requires satisfactory completion of curriculum in contrast to the OBE system that demands achievements of certain learning outcomes of all the courses in the curriculum, to graduate the degree program. Therefore, procedures and methodologies followed in the former system cannot be used as-it-is in the OBE system. However, some HEIs are still following the old procedures in the adaptation of the new system, which eventually leads to the failure of the OBE system. One of the major hindrances in the adaptation of the OBE system is the lack of effective control, without which learning outcomes cannot be achieved. It is thereby very crucial to introduce a well-defined OBE framework, along with the aggressive administration from the higher academic and administrative bodies to play their role in making the HEIs strictly follow the OBE Framework. Also, it is equally important to identify/rectify the unethical practices followed by different HEIs. This whole implementation problem along with its side effects has been thoroughly discussed in this paper as the main scope. This paper also aims to present a strategic solution to the highlighted issues by employing the feedback control theory. The paper, therefore, presents a two-fold contribution. First, the implementation problems of the OBE system are critically analyzed. Next, a few modifications in the existing approaches have been introduced to achieve the desired results from the recently adopted OBE system.

Index Terms: Academic Control System, OBE-Framework, OBE System Implementation, Outcome-Based-Education, Undergraduate Engineering Program.

I. INTRODUCTION

Undergraduate or Bachelor of Engineering Studies is the most fundamental degree program in the cadre of higher engineering education. After successful completion of the degree program, the engineering graduates are expected to be fully equipped with the knowledge of, Fundamental Engineering Principles, Basic Engineering Methods and Techniques, and the relevant Technology of the respective discipline. Any deficiency at this stage is irrecoverable, and it would cause disablement of the graduates in perusing higher studies, and in practicing engineering in the industry. Keeping in view of the importance of the degree program, it is needed to give exceptional care in conducting these studies. The Outcome-Based-Education or OBE system can ensure attainment of all the required goals of the degree program, should it be properly implemented. Owing to its popular merits, the Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC) introduced the OBE system in Pakistan, by signing the Washington Accord.

The Washington Accord created in 1989; is an agreement to accept undergraduate engineering degrees that are obtained using the OBE method. Initially, it was adopted by countries like Australia, South Africa, and the United States in the early 1990s [1-4]. It was followed by other countries like Hong Kong, Malaysia, and the EU [5-7]. By the end of 2017, several countries come on board as the full signatories including, Canada, Taiwan, Pakistan, India, Ireland, Japan, Korea, New Zealand, Russia, Singapore, South Africa, Sri Lanka, Turkey, China, and the United States [8].

The OBE system has widespread acceptance all over the world due to its inherited benefits that include student involvement, clarity in learning objectives, the flexibility of teaching methods, and comparability by different institutions. Despite this fact, several cases of phasing out this mode of education have been reported in literature [6]. The reasons for this phase-out and associated problems faced by these countries are discussed and analyzed in-depth in the references [1-6]. There are many reasons for

the failure of the OBE system, the main reason had been the vague assessment system, and un-thoughtful implementation of the OBE system, without considering the local conditions and ground realities. It is worth mentioning here that, despite having highly qualified teaching faculty (PhDs) and state-of-the-art resources in their bachelor-degree programs; most of the developed countries (like Australia) must face failure in adopting this system.

Provided the fact that OBE is a student-centric approach, that not only emphasizes the achievements of the student at the end of any degree program but also provides some pre-defined parameters to evaluate the said achievement. Several works in the literature are found that emphasize the implementation of the OBE system and the associated teaching methodologies in different countries of the world [9-15]. Since the Higher Education Commission (HEC) of Pakistan introduced OBE to local universities in late 2015, the authors discussed the implementation scheme of the OBE system under a constrained local Pakistani environment [16]. Accordingly, a detailed analysis of transformation from teacher-centric (conventional mode) to OBE is presented [17]. In contrast to these works, [16] and [17], this paper aims to highlight the ways and means to achieve benefits of OBE system implementation, within local (Pakistani) circumstances, and avoid failure due to its weaknesses, by taking preventive and corrective measures. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows; Section II gives a brief idea of the OBE system, followed by a brief explanation of factors it involves. Section III states the key problems along with the OBE framework; in the next section i.e., Section IV, the proposed solution has been stated. Section V gives the modus operandi of the proposed solution. Finally, the conclusion is made in Section VI.

II. BASIC IDEA OF OBE SYSTEM

The OBE-based system degree program comprises of the three main objectives: Program Educational Objective (PEO), Program Learning Outcome (PLO), and Course Learning Outcome (CLO). All these outcomes in an OBE system are well defined and known to both students and teaching staff. This is to ensure that each of them knows after the completion of a degree program, each candidate should achieve a certain set of skills. Therefore, OBE is defined as a closed-loop system and needs a continuous check and balance on yearly basis. Academic authorities of the HEI prepare a report known as Self-Assessment-Report (SAR) for each degree program, which is evaluated by accreditation bodies (such as the Pakistan Engineering Council, in Pakistan) for the certification of the degree program.

III. MAJOR PROBLEMS IN THE EXISTING SYSTEM

In the syllabus and curriculum-based education system, some of the teachers used to teach a selective portion of the syllabus with more emphasis, which is of their main interest. And in doing so, sometimes they ignore teaching an important portion of the syllabus. This would result in incomplete knowledge (or learning outcomes) attainment by the students at the end of the course. In absence of an effective regulatory mechanism, this practice could not be corrected in this system.

Because of the several inherited advantages of the OBE system, PEC introduced it in local engineering HEIs, replacing previously followed syllabus and curriculum-based education system. The previously followed system only requires satisfactory completion of curriculum to graduate the degree program, in contrast to the OBE system that demands achievements of certain learning outcomes of all the courses in the curriculum. Therefore, procedures and methodologies followed in the former system cannot be used as-it-is in the OBE system. However, some HEIs are still following the old procedures in the adaptation of the new system, which eventually leads to the failure of the OBE system. Following are the main problems that are a result of the faulty implementation of the OBE system:

A. Weak CQI Mechanism

Figure 1 shows a functional block diagram of the OBE framework [18]. It is evident from the figure that the OBE system is a Multiple-Input-Multiple-Output (MIMO) academic feedback system, and it makes Continuous-Quality-Improvement (CQI), in a changing environment, to meet the OBE's objectives, PEO, PLO, and CLO. Quality Enhancement Cell (QEC), along with other academic bodies like Board-of-Studies (BOS), Board-of-Faculty (BOF), and Academic Council (AC), is supposed to be responsible for the executing of CQI process. In the presence of an effective CQI mechanism, it is very unlikely that the OBE might be failed. However, the poor implementation of the OBE system can result in; inaccurate measurement and faulty evaluation of learning outcomes, and thus it would result in flawed 'CQI' control actions. Consequently, the achieved learning outcomes would gradually diverge from their required levels, and if the trend is not checked, the whole System can go vagrant and can be failed at the right time of time.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of OBE System Framework [18]

The three OBE system parameters (PEO, PLO, & CLO) are coupled variables, i.e., these parameters are interlinked with each other, and the system is, therefore, a coupled MIMO system. A professional and intelligent approach is required for the CQI mechanism that may give desired results. Like all coupled-MIMO feedback systems, the OBE system can only be beneficial, if and only if all its individual parameters

meet their set targets. Therefore, it is required that all three parameters (PEO, PLO, and CLO) should achieve their desired peaks, within a specified period. In these three parameters, the high achievement of PEO by the HEI Graduates is very much dependent on their academic training and hence reliant on good performances of the rest of the two outcomes: PLO and CLO. Therefore, it is inevitably required that later two parameters (CLO & PLO) should have an effective feedback-control system under strict monitoring and control of the academic officials (with well-defined responsibility and authority). Incorporation of an inner-feedback-control-loop, within the OBE framework, will not only make CQI action more efficient, but it will also help in achieving the desired learning outcomes accurately.

B. Inaccurate Assessment Process

a) Deceptive Assessment:

The vagueness of assessment, of OBE system parameters, is considered as one of the major flaws of the System. Implementation of the OBE system following a classical semester system approach, in which the course in charge has unbridled assessment authority, makes the problem worst. Especially when the students succeed to deceive their assessors by using unfair means in the sessional tests (like; midterm-tests, quizzes, assignments, etc.). Incidentally, this assessment authority cannot be altered, as per the very nature of the semester system. Consequently, due to unavoidable "human error", some students (or graduates) clear the course (with flying marks) without achieving all learning outcomes. Eventually, this causes irreparable damage to society. Therefore, it is required that human-based assessment should be coupled with an unmanned or auto-assessment to filter out the phony graduates from real ones.

b) Course Topics Wise Assessment:

There is another factor that makes the assessment faulty. Some teachers assess their students for all topics of the (old) syllabus, instead of assessing them for the real learning outcomes. For example, syllabi of engineering courses include math topics also, therefore questions made on these math topics only is a wrong practice. It has been observed that some engineering graduates gained expertise in simulation and mathematical tools, and have very poor knowledge of engineering basics. Therefore, CLOs must be properly defined and questions posed in tests, assignments, quizzes, etc., should be based on them. Otherwise, the final assessment will be inaccurate and will not reflect the achievement of real learning outcomes. The main cause of this problem is unscrupulously defining CLOs derived from the old syllabus of the subject course. Knowledge of; engineering principles, engineering methods, or engineering-techniques, etc., should be the learning outcome of an engineering course. Pure Math-topics-based CLO definition is a wrong practice. Academic managers should check and correct it, the QEC and OBE cell experts can help them, in this regard.

IV. PROPOSED IMPLEMENTATION SOLUTION

The objective of the OBE system is to achieve desired learning outcomes (CLO & PLO) from Teaching-Learning

(or Pedagogic) System. Achievement of the goal is not possible until enforcement of an effective regulatory mechanism on its operation. This will assure that; all CLOs must be covered in teaching the course, and the assessment should be made on all of the learning outcomes. Therefore, it is required to introduce an inner feedback control loop in the OBE framework (Figure 1). Secondly, the latest technological aids should also be employed to improve the performance efficiency of the Pedagogic system and to assure accurate assessment of the learning outcomes. The solution will help the overall CQI mechanism to correct the Pedagogic system if it deviates from the reference trajectory and will make it achieve desired learning outcomes. Thus, the proposed solution to the regulation and the CQI problems consists of the following two components:

- Introduction of an inner-feedback-control-loop for academic activity.
- Employment of latest technological tools for the Teaching-Learning and Assessment activities.

A. Internal Feedback Control Loop

The design of the internal feedback control loop is derived from 'Control Theory'. Therefore, it is appropriate to describe the relevant part of the control theory before the explanation of the control-loop design.

a) Feedback Control Theory:

An author Stefan Simrock defined the control theory as follows [19]:

“In engineering and mathematics, control theory deals with the behavior of dynamical systems. The desired output of a system is called the reference. When one or more output variables of a system need to follow a certain reference over time, a controller manipulates the inputs to a system to obtain the desired effect on the output of the system.”

Control theory is based on the following two fundamental postulates (which are being used for designing the academic-feedback-control system):

1. In absence of any control action, it is a rare chance that even a perfectly made system would give the required performance when it is operating under influence of external/environmental forces.
2. The system cannot control itself; it always needs an external controller, which influences the system in such a way that it gives a required performance.

Remark: Another important premise of system theory is derived from the Principle of Inertia, (which originated with Aristotle for "motions in a void", which states that an object tends to resist a change in motion). The premise, being used by the system states that all systems resist change in their present states, i.e., all systems tend to endure their present states of operations and they do resist any external influences or control forces that tend to change the present states.

b) System to be Controlled:

In the old (annual) education system 'Teaching' and 'Learning' were two distinct activities, however, the modern (semester) education system fused both activities into one unified 'Teaching-Learning' activity.

It is to be noted that the aim and objective of the OBE system are to attain required Learning-Outcomes by the students and graduates.

However, students' Learning is dependent on their active participation in:

- Class-Room Lectures,
- Learning-Activity generated by the Course-in-Charges (and their team of; Teaching-Assistants and Lab Assistants).

Therefore, the students-group cannot be separated from its teachers, and consequently, the 'Teaching-Learning' system can be considered as one unit – the Pedagogic system. Following the second postulate of control theory, the Pedagogic system cannot control itself. That is, in absence of appropriate external control actions, it cannot achieve the desired outputs, especially when it is operating under influence of external influences (like; deviation of the set plan by the teachers due to personal reasons, and use of unfair means by the students). The Pedagogic system is human, and each member of it has different nature. It implies that the system-to-be-controlled is random, and therefore it requires an adaptable intelligent controller for its control (or management). Fortunately, variation in the members of the system is known and bounded.

c) Design of Inner-Control-Loop:

The topology of the internal-feedback-control-loop for the academic activity, within the OBE Framework, is illustrated in Figure 2. It is a typical Two-Input-Two-Output (TITO) vectors feedback-control-system aimed to minimize the error between desired and achieved outputs. The 'Academic Controllers' (or Academic Managers) are required to consistently monitor, evaluate, and intelligently control the academic activity, such that the errors between

required-learning outcomes (CLO_R & PLO_R) and achieved-learning outcomes (CLO_A & PLO_A) should become minimum possible. The 'Course-Reports' are being used as a 'Feedback Element', which shall be prepared by the course-in-charge, in the format of "course files" of the PEC Manual of Accreditation (pp. 30-31, [20]).

Based on reported assessment of attained output parameters; CLO_A & PLO_A , (in feedback) the academic controllers (or managers) will *evaluate* the process performances against the desired goals and will take appropriate control actions for minimizing the process errors. Thus, the key role of the controllers is to take appropriate control action; to reject the effects of external influences, and to make the Pedagogic system follow the reference inputs (CLO_R & PLO_R) with negligible steady-state errors within minimum transient-time.

d) The inertia of the Humanoid System:

Transient time primarily depends on the inertia of the System-to-be-Controlled and it is the main hurdle in the initial control phase.

Fortunately, unlike machines, the inertia of human beings is not rigid, as they have the capability of learning and adaptability. However, it requires constant application of controlling efforts to develop their adaptability to the controlled environment. Carrot-and-stick policy is an established controlling instrument. Therefore, expert Academic Managers can adroitly manage this impediment, and with their consistent efforts, all the control objectives would be achieved in minimum possible transient time – that is, minimizing the steady-state process errors to a negligible value, and thusly achieving all the required Learning Outcomes.

Remark: Once the Pedagogic System is adapted to the controlled environment, it will respond immediately to the command inputs (without any hesitations or delays). Even in this situation, control pressures must continuously be applied to the System; otherwise, in its absence, it will go back to square one. (Because of the elastic nature of the human-inertia, it will re-adapt itself to the most convenient or relaxed position.)

Figure 2: Academic Feedback Control Loop for Outcome-Based-Education System

e) Impact on CQI Process:

The cycle period of the Course Report based inner loop is one regular semester. Whereas the cycle period of SAR based overall OBE loop is one academic year. Therefore, Assessment, Evaluation, and Improvement (or CQI process) will be made twice a year due to inner loop, by the HEI's academic managers, and once a year for the whole OBE cycle, by the Academic Experts of the accreditation body. It implies that the frequency of the CQI process will be tripled due to the introduction of the inner control loop. Thence the attainment speed of the required OBE System objectives will become much faster due to the introduction of the inner-control-loop.

B. Employment of latest Technology

a) Teaching Learning Aid:

Use of Teaching-Learning technological aids and LMS (learning-management-system) type IT tools can greatly enhance performance efficiency of the Pedagogic System, and therefore, it is highly recommended for their employment. LMS-associated database tools are helpful for; data-recording, its analysis, and report-generation of semester sessional activity. It also provides an interactive platform (24/7, through the Internet) to all stakeholders of the OBE System, especially the students and the teachers. Thus, the use of technological Learning aids can enhance the performance efficiency of the Pedagogic activity and can help in the accurate Assessment of OBE System parameters.

b) Unmanned Testing System: Conduction of MCQ type filter-testing, on an unmanned auto-assessment testing system, is an essential requirement for minimizing human error in students' final assessment. Students' active participation in the academic activity is expected to result in learning of basic principles of the course. The test will determine this outcome. Fortunately, an auto-assessment or machine testing facility is available in all of the local engineering HEIs, and they administer such kinds of auto-assessment tests in their Admission process.

The diagram shown in Figure-3 illustrates the mechanics of the overall proposed solutions. Besides illustration of the flow of the control process of the Teaching-Learning (or Pedagogic) system, it also shows the role and approach of different academic and non-academic bodies and that of technology-support in solving problems, which were discussed in Section III and Section VI.

V. MODE D'EMPLOI OF PROPOSED SOLUTION

In the previous sections, various facts are investigated and are accordingly stipulated to make final remarks on the implementation of the proposed solution. The remarks cannot be treated as a final verdict; however, these can help achieve desired objectives of the OBE system.

- 1) The sessional academic activity should be monitored and controlled by the Academic Managers, that is; Head-of-Department (HOD), any Academic Body (like BOS), and the Dean of University [or Principal/Head of Institution (HOI), in case of University College].
- 2) Besides simple class Lectures and Labs, the

semester session should have sufficient learning-cum-assessment activities like; Tutorials/Tests, Assignments and Quizzes, etc. The performance of each student should be assessed and recorded after each activity by the course in charge.

- 3) Interactive Analysis & Design Tutorial(s) should be conducted, for application courses. The tutorial should be conducted by a course expert (preferably an industrial expert in the field). This would cover the OBE system requirement for, solving a complex engineering problem. Students' performance shall be assessed, graded, and recorded by the anchorperson of the Tutorial.
 - **Remark:** Above two activities (in 2 & 3) are Learning-cum-Assessment activities, therefore the students should be timely shared with the assessed scripts, corrected reports, and the teacher's solutions.
- 4) At the conclusion of the semester, the Examination Department of the degree-awarding authority institution will administer the MCQ type End Test, which will be based on considerably basic concepts of the entire course, (covering all the CLOs). The test shall be conducted on; an unmanned or auto-assessment testing system.
- 5) For qualifying the End Test, a well-defined yet moderate grading scheme needs to be introduced. For instance, candidates who secured less than 50% marks in the Test, shall straight away be graded F (Fail), and they will have to repeat the course.

Figure 3: Block diagram Illustration of Overall Proposed Solution

- 6) Grades, for the End Test finalists, shall be assigned by the Examination Authority, which

shall be based on the student's assessments at various Bloom's Taxonomy domains.

- **Remark:** As per the OBE System requirement, the final Assessment and Grading should be CLO-based. Successful completion of a course should be conditional for students to acquire a minimum achievement level in each of the CLOs of the course.
- 7) After the announcement of the Final Results, the Course-in-charges shall prepare and submit the Course Reports to the HOD, who will combine them in semester-wise folders. Each folder will contain; relevant Course Reports and their referenced summary prepared by the HOD, in the format of Annex-C of "Manual of Accreditation" of PEC (p. 52, [20]).
 - 8) Subsequently, the HOD will circulate these Folders amongst the selected Academic Managers, such as Non-Teaching Faculty Members (or the External Members) of BOS, and the University Dean (or, Principal/HOI) for their evaluation and Improvement advice or recommendations.
 - **Remark-I:** In Academic Managers, only HOD can be a part of the teaching faculty. External BOS Members and Dean (or Principal/HOI) must not be having any teaching responsibility in the related Department; otherwise, they will not be eligible for the Evaluation-and-Control assignment.
 - **Remark-II:** Eligible Dean (or Principal/HOI) is the Chief (or Master) Controller. Therefore, the recommendations made by him shall be binding for all his subordinates, which includes HOD and all members of the Pedagogic System.
 - 9) The teaching faculty will prepare course plans for next Semester as per the improvement advice of the Academic Managers. The Plans will be timely communicated to students and HOD.
 - 10) HOD will ensure implementation of the; Course Plans and Improvement Recommendations, by his constant supervisory control of the performance of the Pedagogic System's sessional activity.
 - **Remark:** By employment of LMS, the HOD can monitor the up-to-date progress of the sessional activity of each course on his computer screen.

This solution will provide a regulatory mechanism, which will guarantee the achievement of desired learning outcomes by the engineering graduates. It will also help improve the quality of education, and therefore, it will further strengthen the overall CQI mechanism that the HEIs are operating under Quality-Enhancement-Cell (QEC).

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a study is conducted to investigate the right implementation problem of the OBE system and find its

solution, which can ensure the achievement of all benefits of the OBE system. Summarizing the study, the following conclusions can be made:

OBE System is a new system for Pakistani engineering HEIs. In fact, most of our engineering institutions are still in the transition phase of converting previously employed Syllabus and Curriculum-based education systems into the Outcome Based Education system. In this transition period, some of the old academic practices are still being observed in the adaptation of the new system. As the two systems have altogether different basic principles therefore some of these old practices cannot be used as-it-is in fruitful implementation of the OBE system. After detailed analysis, it is highlighted that requirement of the new system must be clearly understood and must be fulfilled. QEC and OBE Cell should play an active role in this regard. It is pleaded that:

- CLOs of the courses must be judiciously specified. That is, the definition of CLOs must be based on the main knowledge areas of the course. QEC and OBE experts should train the Teaching Faculty, in this regard.
- The QEC and OBE Cell must also play their role in all august academic bodies (BOS, BOF, AC, etc.) to change the old and faulty academic practices as per the OBE system.

Implementation of the OBE system by the currently practicing CQI mechanism, which is based on inaccurate Assessment, (resulting) faulty Evaluation, and a loose Control, will not be fruitful. Therefore, to solve the imperfect OBE System implementation problem, it is proposed that:

- Usage of technological Teaching-Learning Aids and that of the Computing and IT tools is the need of the hour. It can significantly enhance the Pedagogic system's performance efficiency and can ensure accurate and speedy Assessment.
- Students' final Assessments in each course should be CLO-based. Successful completion of a course should be conditional for students to acquire a minimum achievement level in each of the CLOs of the course.
- To fast track and regulate the Academic Activity, the introduction of an internal-feedback-control loop (within OBE Framework) is inevitable. It will also enable improvement of the overall Evaluation process and will improve the effectiveness of the CQI mechanism for the achievement of the OBE System's objectives.

The solution proposed in this study modifies and corrects the non-OBE-based academic practices, inherited from the previously followed system, and thence, it resolves the faulty implementation problem of the OBE system. Secondly, it introduces a regulatory mechanism, which makes the Pedagogic system obey rules and regulations of the OBE system, in its true spirit. And finally, it guarantees; the attainment of all learning outcomes by the engineering graduates and makes them ready for playing their role in the accomplishment of Program Educational Objectives (PEO) in their professional life.

Post Script:

We would like to conclude the paper with a final request to PEC and HEC of redefining the minimum Teaching Faculty Strength for undergraduate degree programs. OBE System effective implementation has imposed an extra burden on Teaching Faculty, as compared to the workload used to have in the previous system. Therefore, it is highly recommended that the present minimum Strength may please be enhanced, and the role of the Teaching and Lab Assistants should also be acknowledged by assigning an appropriate strength in the said Standard.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank PAF-Karachi Institute of Economics and Technology, Karachi, Pakistan, for all the support provided to accomplish this research work.

Authors Contributions

The paper is a brainchild of Ashab Mirza, which is based on his experience of introducing and administering the OBE System in 2018 at the *Institute of Industrial Electronics Engineering (IIEE)* as Principal-IIEE. In his 34 years of professional services (1986-2020) to Industry-Academia (SUPARCO & IIEE), he has 31 years of engineering educational experience; that is, from 1989 to 1997, on a part-time basis in different local engineering HEIs (including NED UET) and afterward on regular basis at IIEE, PCSIR (1997-2020). On the basis of his exposure to standard and quality (local and international) engineering education, his experience of OBE System administration, and his interaction with different professionals of engineering education from different HEIs of the country, he conceived the idea of this paper. Finally, he came up with this paper, with the help of his able and expert co-author. Therefore, his main contribution to this study was the concept development, correspondence, supervision, and methodology.

Saba Javed is an experienced faculty member of PAF KEIT (2011-To date). She also completed her Ph.D. studies in Electrical Engineering from this Institution. Her main contribution in this paper was the project administration, and paper writing.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest between all the authors.

Data Availability Statement

No testing data is available in this paper.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

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